

Expanding Comics Beyond Sight: Shapereader's Conceptual comics and tactile narratives

Wednesday, November 13, 2024
04:15 PM - 05:15 PM

Location:

Zoom

Cost:

Free

Web:

<https://sfsu.zoom.us/meeting/register/tZctd-2urTMiG9NE6i7OtWUKSBVi65V3nU7q#/registration> (<https://sfsu.zoom.us/meeting/register/tZctd-2urTMiG9NE6i7OtWUKSBVi65V3nU7q#/registration>)

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Join Comics Studies @ SFState Wednesday, November 13, for a conversation with conceptual comics artist Ilan Manouach! Belgian conceptual comics artist Ilan Manouach is a leading innovator for outside-the-box comics. From provocative reworkings of beloved classics to his recent work developing synthetic AI comics, Manouach's thought-producing pieces push us to think about comics in new ways. Join us Wednesday, November 13, at 4:15, as he shares about one of his past innovations, Shapereader, a tactile comic, that uses tactile ideograms to invent new means of textual storytelling. The discussion of Shapereader will set the stage to better understand conceptual comics and their potential. Join us in person in HUM 587 Wednesday, November 13, at 4:15 or register to view his talk virtually on Zoom here: <https://tinyurl.com/comicsNov13>. For any access questions, contact Emily Beitiks, beitiks@sfsu.edu.

Save to: Windows Live Calendar ([http://calendar.live.com/calendar/calendar.aspx?rru=addevent&summary=Expanding Comics Beyond Sight: Shapereader's Conceptual comics and tactile narratives&dtstart=20241113T161500&dtend=20241113T171500&description=Join Comics Studies @ SFState Wednesday, November 13, for a conversation with conceptual comics artist Ilan Manouach! Belgian conceptual comics artist Ilan Manouach is a leading innovator for outside-the-box comics. From provocative reworkings of beloved classics to his recent work developing synthetic AI comics, Manouach's thought-producing pieces push us to think about comics in new ways. Join us Wednesday, November 13, at 4:15, as he shares about one of his past innovations, Shapereader, a tactile comic, that uses tactile ideograms to invent new means of textual storytelling. The discussion of Shapereader will set the stage to better understand conceptual comics and their potential. Join us in person in HUM 587 Wednesday, November 13, at 4:15 or register to view his talk virtually on Zoom here: <https://tinyurl.com/comicsNov13>. For any access questions, contact Emily Beitiks, \[beitiks@sfsu.edu\]\(mailto:beitiks@sfsu.edu\).&location=Zoom](http://calendar.live.com/calendar/calendar.aspx?rru=addevent&summary=Expanding+Comics+Beyond+Sight:+Shapereader's+Conceptual+comics+and+tactile+narratives&dtstart=20241113T161500&dtend=20241113T171500&description=Join+Comics+Studies+@+SFState+Wednesday,+November+13,+for+a+conversation+with+conceptual+comics+artist+Ilan+Manouach!+Belgian+conceptual+comics+artist+Ilan+Manouach+is+a+leading+innovator+for+outside-the-box+comics.+From+provocative+reworkings+of+beloved+classics+to+his+recent+work+developing+synthetic+AI+comics,+Manouach's+thought-producing+pieces+push+us+to+think+about+comics+in+new+ways.+Join+us+Wednesday,+November+13,+at+4:15,+as+he+shares+about+one+of+his+past+innovations,+Shapereader,+a+tactile+comic,+that+uses+tactile+ideograms+to+invent+new+means+of+textual+storytelling.+The+discussion+of+Shapereader+will+set+the+stage+to+better+understand+conceptual+comics+and+their+potential.+Join+us+in+person+in+HUM+587+Wednesday,+November+13,+at+4:15+or+register+to+view+his+talk+virtually+on+Zoom+here:+https://tinyurl.com/comicsNov13.+For+any+access+questions,+contact+Emily+Beitiks,+beitiks@sfsu.edu.&location=Zoom)) - Google Calendar ([https://www.google.com/calendar/event?action=TEMPLATE&text=Expanding Comics Beyond Sight: Shapereader's Conceptual comics and tactile narratives&dates=20241113T161500%2F20241113T171500&details=Join Comics Studies @ SFState Wednesday, November 13, for a conversation with conceptual comics artist Ilan Manouach! Belgian conceptual comics artist Ilan Manouach is a leading innovator for outside-the-box comics. From provocative reworkings of beloved classics to his recent work developing synthetic AI comics, Manouach's thought-producing pieces push us to think about comics in new ways. Join us Wednesday, November 13, at 4:15, as he shares about one of his past innovations, Shapereader, a tactile comic, that uses tactile ideograms to invent new means of textual storytelling. The discussion of Shapereader will set the stage to better understand conceptual comics and their potential. Join us in person in HUM 587 Wednesday, November 13, at 4:15 or register to view his talk virtually on Zoom here: <https://tinyurl.com/comicsNov13>. For any access questions, contact Emily Beitiks, \[beitiks@sfsu.edu\]\(mailto:beitiks@sfsu.edu\).&location=Zoom](https://www.google.com/calendar/event?action=TEMPLATE&text=Expanding+Comics+Beyond+Sight:+Shapereader's+Conceptual+comics+and+tactile+narratives&dates=20241113T161500%2F20241113T171500&details=Join+Comics+Studies+@+SFState+Wednesday,+November+13,+for+a+conversation+with+conceptual+comics+artist+Ilan+Manouach!+Belgian+conceptual+comics+artist+Ilan+Manouach+is+a+leading+innovator+for+outside-the-box+comics.+From+provocative+reworkings+of+beloved+classics+to+his+recent+work+developing+synthetic+AI+comics,+Manouach's+thought-producing+pieces+push+us+to+think+about+comics+in+new+ways.+Join+us+Wednesday,+November+13,+at+4:15,+as+he+shares+about+one+of+his+past+innovations,+Shapereader,+a+tactile+comic,+that+uses+tactile+ideograms+to+invent+new+means+of+textual+storytelling.+The+discussion+of+Shapereader+will+set+the+stage+to+better+understand+conceptual+comics+and+their+potential.+Join+us+in+person+in+HUM+587+Wednesday,+November+13,+at+4:15+or+register+to+view+his+talk+virtually+on+Zoom+here:+https://tinyurl.com/comicsNov13.+For+any+access+questions,+contact+Emily+Beitiks,+beitiks@sfsu.edu.&location=Zoom)) - Exchange/Cal ([/public/webcalendar/event/58348.ics](http://public/webcalendar/event/58348.ics))

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